

Social

COMPARATIVE STUDY RELATED TO IMPACT OF TEACHER MOTHER FOR TODDLERS

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Abstract

It is widely accepted that teacher's expectations affect students' achievement. A teacher knows very well how to communicate knowledge to students according to their age, class and mental level of children. Present study is focused on finding of impact of teacher mother and non teacher mother on progress of children.

Keywords: Teacher's Expectations; Academics; Student Achievement.

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1. Introduction

A mother is considered as first teacher of child and a teacher treat student as her child. A mother as a teacher knows the academic need of child and inspires him to get achievement. She knows the way to transmit the knowledge and to develop child's interest in studies and in creative works. A teacher mother has better understanding about emotions of child. The presence of a teacher mother with child effectively reduces their anxiety. A teacher mother is more capable mother for betterment of child. A successful teacher behaves like mother to understand their emotions.

2. Objective of Study

- Finding of impact of teacher mother on student academic progress
- Finding of impact of non teacher mother on student academic progress
- Finding of impact of teacher mother on student non academic progress
- Finding of impact of non teacher mother on student non academic progress

3. Hypothesis

- 1) There is significant impact of teacher mother on academic progress of student.
- 2) There is significant impact of teacher mother on non academic progress of student.
- 3) There is no significant impact of non teacher mother on academic progress of student.
- 4) There is no significant impact of non teacher mother on non academic progress of student.

4. Methodology

Descriptive method was used for present study. 500 students of class I-V were randomly selected as sample. It consists of 125 rural male, 125 rural female, 125 urban male and 125 urban female. They were categorized according to status of working of mother. These students were tested using a self prepared questionnaire. Collected data was tabulated and analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t value as statistical tools.

5. Finding and Analysis

Table 1: Status of Academic and Non Academic Mean Value of Teacher and Non Teacher Mother

Status of Mother	Student Progress	Student Progress		
		Mean Value	Std. Deviation	t value
Teacher Mother	Academic	63.8	1.07	0.88
	Non Academic	54.3	0.92	
Non Teacher Mother	Academic	56.7	1.13	0.91
	Non Academic	59.4	1.02	

Chart: Status of Academic and Non Academic Mean Value of Teacher and Non Teacher Mother

Data shows that students of teacher mother have mean value 63.8 with standard deviation 1.07 and t value calculated as 0.88. This value is significant hence hypothesis 1, there is a significant impact of teacher mother on academic progress of student is accepted.

Non academic mean value of teacher mother students is 54.3 with standard deviation 0.92. Thus hypothesis 2, there is significant impact of teacher mother on non academic progress of student is rejected.

Academic value of students having non teacher mother is 56.7 which is less for teacher mother. Standard deviation is 1.13 and calculated t value is 0.91. Therefore, hypothesis 3, there is no significant impact of non teacher mother on academic progress of student is accepted.

Non academic progress mean value for non teacher mother student is 59.4 greater than the value for teacher mother. That's why hypothesis 4, there is no significant impact of non teacher mother on non academic progress of student is rejected.

6. Conclusion

Teacher mothers influence academic progress of children. A teacher mother influence student academic progress, hence academic results are better in case of teacher mother rather than non teacher mother. In case of non academic progress feedback of students having non teacher mother are better in comparison of teacher mother's child.

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